

EERA Network: 06. Open Learning: Media, Environments and Cultures

Symposium "Free and Open Learning: from its merits to practices"

Free/Libre & Open Source Software: Technology of the Oppressed

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[In the future...]

**"The acquisition of wealth is no longer the driving force in our lives.
We work to better ourselves and the rest of humanity."**

-Jean Luc Picard, Star Trek: First Contact

[Free Software]

Freedom to run, copy, distribute, study, change and improve the software (FSF, 2013).

Not freeware (access)!

F0 to run the program for any purpose.

F1 to study how the program works and change it to make it do what you wish.

F2 to redistribute copies.

F3 to distribute copies of your modified versions to others.

[Free Software]

[Open Source]

Origin tied to tech problem

Origin tied to tech problem

Almost same licenses

Almost same licenses

Vast social impact

Vast social impact

Political
Philosophical
oriented

Marketing/business oriented
community-based
development

Conceptually different

Same concept, new approach

Activism

Institutional, lobbying

the historical narrative of the schism

[Free/Libre & Open Source]

F/LOSS as an alternative way to read and live in today's world that carries an important transformative potential of Foundational, Evincive and Inspirational nature.

Foundational: the implications of the answers materialized by this movement are wider as it embodies an world view

Evincive: provides tools and hints on the implementation

Inspirational: inspires others to act

[Proprietary software]

Software tends to abundance:
Non-rivalrous consumption — — —
No additional costs for additional users

↓
Exclusion and control
mechanisms are imposed

↓
To artificially
create scarcity

↓
Protect material
rights of the owners — — — —

Commodification of
software

Creates incentives
to development

[Proprietary Software]

Programmers are driven by
self-interest

Work is organized around external incentives
Towards the accumulation of wealth

Software development
model based on competition

[“economics of the present”]

Human beings are driven
by self-interest

Work is organized around external incentives
Towards the accumulation of wealth

Society development model
based on competition

[A wider picture...]

- > “end of history” and the victory of liberal democracy (Fukuyama, 1992)
- > world became “flat” laying the ground to a new era of global wealth, peace and freedom powered by free trade, deregulation, economic liberalization and worldwide competition (Friedman, 2007)
- > “[global] companies command as much if not more power than many governments, not only to create value but also to transmit values” (Friedman, 2007, p. 508)

“end of alternatives” also reads as...

[A wider picture...]

- > 2/3 of the world population is excluded from the Internet
- > Corporations (or blockbusters) with revenues > than GDPs
- > (USA) distribution of wealth is becoming less egalitarian
- > (USA) 90% media published by 6 companies
- > Corporations shaping identity and social behavior (EULA, Disneyfication, etc.)

[F/LOSS: evincive]

F/LOSS also provides examples and tools that support the potential of non-proprietary and peer-based strategies of production within a wider scope.

commons-based peer production (Benkler, 2006) or mass collaboration (Tapscott & Williams, 2007)

 **creative
commons**

[F/LOSS: inspirational]

Free Software as an ethical choice towards a society and culture based on the free exchange of ideas and that refuses the domination of the artificial barriers that benefit only a few.

[F/LOSS in Education]

Why using F/LOSS in education (FSF, 2011):

- a) "Schools should teach the value of sharing by setting an example",
- b) social responsibility ("not allow proprietary software companies to impose their power on the rest of society and its future"),
- c) independence from any commercial interests and avoid vendor lock-in
- d) "students are free to study how the programs work and to learn how to adapt them for their own needs",
- e) financial savings
- f) the overall quality of available F/LOSS

[F/LOSS in Education]

(Althusser, 1971; Bordieu and Passeron, 1990; Gramsci, 2000; Freire, 2005; among others)

Education is not a politically neutral human endeavor:
reproducing/legitimizing or emancipation/empowerment

Whom does Education serve?

Whom does Technology serve?

Who owns the software?

But because software is not only a (proprietary) product... who owns the digital means of production, storing and distribution?

[F/LOSS in Education]

[F/LOSS in Education]

Education can be a tool to “read and write the world” (Freire & Macedo, 2005), support the critically process of developing an understanding of how the “world” functions and how to participate in its transformation.

<http://www.freesoftwaremagazine.com>

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[F/LOSS in Education]

In the digital world, F/LOSS raises serious questions (beyond access, features, etc.) to society and education.

It also proves that alternatives are possible and aren't "dead".

We tend to rush into the "next big thing" without questioning the path.

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IMAGES

Screen 2: adapted from Google Maps

Screen 4: adapted from "organize!" by worker (<http://openclipart.org/detail/102679/organize!-by-worker>)

Screen 5: "Heckert GNU white" by Anomie (http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/File:Heckert_GNU_white.svg) & "Tux" by Tene (<http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/File:Tux.png>)

Screen 6: composition based on "crashing wave" by johnny automatic (http://openclipart.org/detail/3166/crashing-wave-by-johnny_automatic), "comic characters: flag" by nicubuntu (<http://openclipart.org/detail/21872/comic-characters:-flag-by-nicubunu>), "free software gang" (<http://www.fsf.org/working-together/gang>) and organization logos

Screen 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15: OpenLab ESEV image archive

Screen 19: nafergo